

Family Environment, Motivation of the Spirit of Learning the Online System at The Kaltara University

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ABSTRACT: The family environment and learning motivation are important factors that greatly influence students' enthusiasm for learning, especially in learning using the online system during the Covid-19 pandemic. On the basis of these problems, this research will focus more on the family environment and learning motivation on students' enthusiasm for learning in online learning. This study aims to analyze the role of the family environment on student enthusiasm for learning through student motivation at the University of Kaltara during the Covid 19 pandemic. This study uses a quantitative approach using a survey method. The research period is five (5) months. The sample of this study amounted to 187 respondents using the slovin formula. The data analysis tool used in this research is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. From the results of the study, it can be concluded that the family environment has influence on the spirit of learning and motivation to learn, with family economic indicators.

KEYWORDS: Online Learning, Family Environment, Learning Motivation, University of Kaltara

I. INTRODUCTION

The world of education in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 has a great impact on changes in the pattern of human life. this is evidenced by the development of the industrial world such as technology, information and communication. This technological development has given rise to various innovations, both distance learning (online/online) whose interaction is through a network system without face-to-face contact (Husaini, 2014; Nurul and Rafsanjani, 2021).

In connection with the government's recommendation to implement WFH (Work From Home), The family environment is one of the important factors that can affect the level of student success, and the education obtained by students also comes from the family (Slameto, 2010; Wahid, et al., 2020). The family environment is the closest environment to us and is a source of motivation that greatly influences us, especially during the online lecture period, there are many factors that decrease the motivation for lectures, such as inadequate internet network connections, lack of understanding of the material provided, feelings of boredom or boredom, and emotional feelings between lecturers and students when lecturing online. The family environment greatly determines the level of achievement of a child's learning outcomes, that learning outcomes are influenced by the family environment (Utaminingsyas, et al., 2020).

With this problem, it is necessary to have motivation, motivation can be a source of encouragement that greatly influences the consistency of enthusiasm in learning. If the

motivation that is built is good, the enthusiasm that is actualized in learning will also be good. Motivation is one that influences success in student learning activities. Without encouragement or motivation, the accepted learning process will be difficult so as to achieve the desired success (Agustina and Hamdu, 2011). The level of success of a child's learning can also be influenced by the role of the family environment, empathy for children has an influence on the formation of thinking patterns and achievements (Handayani, 2017).

Learning motivation is a driving tool in a person so that without realizing it can lead to optimal learning activities, which lead directly to the goals to be achieved, effective teaching and learning processes and expected learning achievements. Motivation is divided into two, namely intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Motivation is very closely related to achievement, so it is very important because its existence is supported by many factors (Putra and Frianto, 2018; Ladd and Sorensen, 2017).

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

HRM Human Resource Management

HRM is a field of management that specifically studies the relationship and role of humans in corporate organizations. HRM, namely humans who become objects within an organization are workers in a company, the focus is related to human labor only. Humans always play an active and dominant role in every organizational activity, because humans are planners, actors, and determinants of the realization of organizational goals (Adamy, 2016).

Family environment

Human education starts from the family, in the family there is the role of parents as educators and children as educated. The family is an educational institution that does not have an official program such as a formal educational institution. What children get in the family will later become the basis and be developed for the next life. According to Hasbullah (2012) the family environment is the first educational environment, because this family is the first time children get education and guidance. The family is a small group that has a leader and members, in which there are duties and work, rights and obligations for each member. The family is the first and foremost place where children learn.

Motivation

According to Hamalik (2011) that motivation is a change in energy in a person which is characterized by the emergence of feelings and reactions to achieve goals. Motivation is the thing that causes, distributes and supports human behavior so that they want to work hard and enthusiastically in order to achieve optimal results. Basically the function of motivation in learning is to encourage humans to carry out an activity based on meeting needs, determining the direction of the goals to be achieved, determining the actions that must be done (Uno, 2021).

Learning motivation is a driving factor for student learning outcomes because of self-study motivation. Motivation is the desire to activate, move, channel, direct the attitudes and behavior of individuals in learning, with motivation having a positive effect on the spirit of learning (Dimiyati and Mudjiono, 2013).

Readiness to learn can arise due to factors from students and their environment. Factors that come from the students themselves usually involve the physical and psychological conditions of a student including learning discipline, student motivation from external factors can be influenced by the student's environment such as family, relationships, home atmosphere, economic conditions, understanding of parents (Slameto, 2010).

Eager to learn

Spirit has the meaning of all activities that will be carried out in line with the mind without any feeling that hinders it, the spirit functions as an inner mover to act (Ruslani and Nurfaejriah, 2015). The spirit of learning is when we do activities in learning, it gives a sense of pleasure in ourselves and becomes more productive. In addition, the spirit of learning will reflect the condition of students being enthusiastic when the student is never absent, and assignments are submitted on time.

The spirit of learning is the desire, the sincerity of a person to do a good job, discipline, to achieve maximum learning, willingness, and deep pleasure in the learning being carried out. The inner spirit creates motivation in learning, learning without enthusiasm will feel boring, not all student learning

is driven by their own spirit factor, some develop their enthusiasm for the subject matter due to the influence of who teaches them, their friends, and their parents (Hasibuan, 2014).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used in this research is quantitative. The primary data collection uses a survey, with a literature study to obtain a theoretical basis that can be used as the basis for an empirical study. After that, it was continued with field observations, for data collection, the data collected was then analyzed

Population and Sample

The research sample used the slovin formula as many as 187 respondents from a total of 572 students University of Kaltara from class 2017 to 2020. This research was conducted at the University of Kaltara Tanjung Selor campus. Implementation time is carried out for 5 (five) months. Variables analyzed include family environment variables, motivation and enthusiasm for student learning. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires, direct interviews with those deemed necessary and literature studies. The data analysis used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SPSS-AMOS 20 software.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The characteristics of Kaltara University students who became respondents in the study based on gender, age, faculty, and year of class are as follows;

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Karakteristik	Jumlah Mahasiswa	Persentasi (%)
Jenis Kelamin		
Laki-laki	56	29,9 %
Perempuan	131	70,1 %
Usia (Tahun)		
15 – 19	27	14 %
20 – 29	160	86 %
Fakultas		
Ekonomi	71	38 %
Fisipol	55	29 %
Tehnik	27	15 %
Pertanian	22	12%
Mipa	12	6%
Tahun Angkatan		
2017	78	41%
2018	51	28%
2019	34	18%
2020	24	13%
Jumlah	187	100 %

Source: Primary Data Results (2022)

Based on the data in table 1, it is known that the characteristics of the respondents based on gender are mostly female, namely 70.1% of students (131), and 29.9% (56) are male, based on age, most are between the ages of 20-29 years. with a total of 86% (160) students, and 27 students (14%) aged 15–19 years. The characteristics based on the most

faculties are Economics, which is 71 students or 38%, followed by Fisipol as many as 55 students or 29%, Engineering 27 students or 15%, Agriculture 22 students or 12%, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences 12 students or 6%. and the Class Year of Unikal students, in this case the most respondents were the class in 2017 which amounted to 78 students or 41% and the least was in the class of 2020, which was 24 students or 13%.

Variable Description Analysis Results

Based on the data in table 2 shows that the variables of the family environment, learning motivation and enthusiasm for learning in the study, have an average value on each indicator between 3.20-4.47, with each variable average value in the family environment of 4.05, 4.08 learning motivation and 4.08 enthusiasm for learning. From the score of each variable, it shows that the respondents gave very good value criteria, according to opinion Tontowi, (2016) that the higher the respondent's score, the better the score, on the other hand, if the score is lower, the value will be less.

Table 2 Analysis Results Description

Lingkungan Keluarga (X)		Motivasi Belajar (Y1)		Semangat Belajar (Y2)	
Korelasi	Rata-rata	Indikator	Rata-rata	Indikator	Rata-rata
X1	4,29	X11	4,38	X21	3,97
X2	4,30	X12	4,43	X22	4,19
X3	4,35	X13	4,26	X23	4,07
X4	4,21	X14	4,47	X24	4,21
X5	3,97	X15	4,23	X25	3,89
X6	3,87	X16	3,37	X26	4,24
X7	4,13	X17	3,39	X27	4,07
X8	4,14	X18	4,06	X28	4,00
X9	4,09	X19	3,83		
X10	3,20	X20	4,44		
Rata-rata Variabel = 4,05		Rata-rata Variabel = 4,08		Rata-rata Variabel = 4,08	

Source: Primary Data Results (2022)

SEM Analysis Test Results

Prior to the SEM analysis, the assumptions of normality, linearity, outliers and multicollinearity were tested. shows that the graphical SEM analysis can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SEM analysis
Source: Primary Data Results 2022

Family environment (X) has a significant effect on the spirit of learning (Y2). This can be seen from the p-value of $0.001 < 0.05$. because the coefficient is positive at 0.42. shows that the relationship between the two is unidirectional, meaning that the better the family environment, the higher the enthusiasm for learning. However, the family environment (X) has no significant effect on learning motivation (Y1). This can be seen from the p-Value of $0.0642 > 0.05$, meaning that regardless of the value of the Family Environment, it will not affect the high or low value of learning motivation.

Learning motivation (Y1) has no significant effect on learning enthusiasm (Y2). It can be seen from the p-Value of $0.756 > 0.05$. This means that regardless of the value of Learning Motivation, it will not affect the high or low value of the Spirit of Learning. Family Environment Variables (X) on Learning Motivation (Y1) and learning enthusiasm (Y2), the results of the indirect effect coefficient are 0.013, meaning that the higher the Learning Environment coefficient value, the higher the Learning Environment coefficient will not affect the value of Learning Spirit through the Learning Motivation variable.

Influence Variable Family Environment (X) and Learning Motivation (Y1) affect the variation of the data on the Variable Spirit of Learning by 0.18 or 18%. The remaining 82% is influenced by factors not examined in this study.

V. DISCUSSION

The Influence of the Family Environment on the Spirit of Learning

From the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the relationship between the Family Environment and the Spirit of Learning is 0.42 with a p-Value of 0.001. Because the p-Value < 0.05 , it indicates this relationship is unidirectional, that the learning environment has a significant effect on learning motivation. This means that the better the learning environment, the higher the student's enthusiasm for learning. In accordance with the opinion of Nurhasnah (2012) that the family environment and self-efficacy have an influence on student learning outcomes and affect learning achievement. In addition to these factors, there are other factors that can determine the achievement of learning outcomes, namely internal and external factors such as the individual himself (health), intelligence and talent, interests and motivation and learning methods, while external factors such as family, school, community and the surrounding environment (Dalyono, 2007).

Based on the results of descriptive statistics, it shows that the average value of the largest Family Environment indicator variable is the way parents educate (X1 and X2), while the average value of the largest learning spirit variable indicator is the quality to survive (Y3 and Y4). Descriptive statistical data shows that the average value of the learning

environment variable is very good, as well as the average value of the learning enthusiasm variable is also very good.

Based on the SEM analysis test, itNote that the family environment is measured by five aspects, each of which has a value/weight, namely, the way parents educate 0.65, family relationships 0.73, home atmosphere 0.49, family economic situation 0.75, and family understanding 0.63. Where the fourth aspect, namely the family economy is the most important as a measure of the Family Environment. This indicates that the high value of the Family Environment is mainly seen from the economic aspect of the family. While the Spirit of Learning measured by four aspects, each of which has a value/weight, namely, high discipline of 0.44, quality of survival of 0.65, quantity against frustration of 0.67, and group spirit of 0.67. The third and fourth aspects, namely the quantity against frustration and the spirit of the group are the most important as a measure of enthusiasm for learning. This indicates that the high value of enthusiasm for learning will mainly be seen in the aspect of strength against frustration and group spirit.

From the results of the analysis, it is stated that the better the family environment will have a positive effect on the higher the enthusiasm for learning in students. This shows that if there is an increase in the family environment, which is mainly in the aspect of the family's economic situation, it will result in an increase in learning enthusiasm which will be obtained mainly from the aspect of Strength against frustration and group spirit.

The Influence of Family Environment on Learning Motivation

From the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the relationship between the family environment and learning motivation is 0.04 with a p-value of 0.0642. Because the p-value > 0.05, it indicates that the family environment has no significant effect on learning motivation. This means that the family environment has a relatively small effect on learning motivation.

Based on the results of descriptive statistics show that the average value of the largest family environment variable indicator is the way parents educate (X1 and X2), while the average value on the indicator of the largest learning motivation variable is physiological needs (X11 and X12). Descriptive statistical data shows that the average value of the family environment variable is very good, and the average value of the learning motivation variable is also very good

Based on the SEM analysis test, itNote that the family environment is measured by five aspects, each of which has a value/weight, namely, the way parents educate 0.65, family relationships 0.73, home atmosphere 0.49, family economic situation 0.75, and family understanding 0.63. Where the fourth aspect, namely the family economy is the most important as a measure of the Family Environment. This indicates that the high value of the Family Environment is mainly seen from the economic aspect of the family.

Based on the SEM analysis test shows that learning motivation is measured by five aspects, each of which has a value / weight, namely physiological needs of 0.51, security needs of 0.74, social needs of 0.70, esteem needs of 0.57 and the need for actuation is 0.56, where the second aspect, namely the need for security, is the most important as a measure of learning motivation. This indicates that the high motivation to learn will mainly be seen in the aspect of the need for a sense of security.this is because with a sufficient family economy it gives a lot of time to gather with family, and vice versa. According to opinionKhafid and Suroso (2007) that the family environment has a significant effect on economic learning outcomes, and learning discipline has a significant effect on economic learning outcomes.

From the results of the analysis, it is stated that the family environment has no significant effect on learning motivation. This shows that if there is an increase in the Family Environment which is mainly seen from the aspect of the family's economic situation, it will have a relatively small effect on learning motivation, which will be obtained, mainly seen from the aspect of the need for security.Motivation is a series of efforts or actions of someone who wants to do something (Sardiman, 2011). According to Slameto, (2003) motivation is a process that can increase the spirit in us in carrying out activities according to one's interests, concepts, attitudes and so on.

The Effect of Motivation on the Spirit of Learning

From the results of the analysis, the coefficient of the relationship between learning motivation and enthusiasm for learning is 0.03 with a p-value of 0.756. Because the p-Value > 0.05, it indicates that learning motivation has no significant effect on learning enthusiasm. It is said to have an insignificant effect, meaning that learning motivation has a relatively small effect on the spirit of learning

From the results of descriptive statistics show that the average value of the largest learning motivation variable indicator is physiological needs (X11 and X12), while the average value of the largest learning motivation variable indicator is the quality to survive (Y3 and Y4). Descriptive statistical data shows that the average value of the learning motivation variable is very good, as well as the average value of the learning motivation variable is also very good.

Based on the SEM analysis test, it shows that learning motivation is measured in five aspects, namely physiological needs, security needs, social needs, esteem needs and actualization needs, where the second aspect, namely the need for safety, is the most important as a measure of learning motivation. This shows that the high value of Learning Motivation is mainly seen from the aspect of the need for security. Meanwhile, the spirit of learning is measured by four aspects, namely high discipline, quality of survival, quantity against frustration and group spirit. The third and fourth aspects, namely the quantity of fighting frustration and

group spirit are the most important as a measure of enthusiasm for learning.

From the results of the analysis, it is stated that learning motivation has no significant effect on the spirit of learning. This shows that if there is an increase in learning motivation which is mainly seen from the need for security, it has a relatively small effect on the perceived enthusiasm for learning, mainly seen from the quantity against frustration and group spirit. According to Andarita, (2013) that with a high mindset (IQ), students will not easily experience depression/frustration and learning motivation will affect the spirit of learning.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study concluded that the family environment has an influence on the spirit of learning and learning motivation, with family economic indicators, so that students who have high learning motivation will be more enthusiastic in learning so that they get good results. So it is recommended that in the online learning process to increase students' motivation to learn, the family environment must continue to accompany and support students in learning.

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